

AGRICULTURAL MARKETING- A STUDY ON MARKETING OF PADDY

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ABSTRACT

This paper makes an attempt to study the magnitude, determinants, marketing channels and distress sale of marketed surplus of paddy across the different villages and farm sizes under study in Subarnapur district of Odisha state. The marketable surplus is found positively influenced by the size of output and nature of market for selling it. The informal marketing channel is more active in the area and formal (regulated market) are mostly beneficial to higher farm sizes. Hence Distress sale takes place despite various policies of the government. The strategy for paddy marketing may be revamped.

Key Words:- Paddy Marketing, Marketed Surplus, credit inter-linkages.

1.1 Introduction

The marketed surplus involves various related aspects such as production, farm size, marketing channels, relative price, nature of crops, family size and their consumption habits, credit inter-linkages, information and infrastructural issues etc. across various farm sizes and villages with varied level of agricultural development.

Often the term "Marketable surplus" and "Marketed surplus" are used as synonyms even though theoretically certain distinctions exist between these. The marketable surplus refers to the quantity which is the excess or residual left with the producer-farmer after meeting his genuine requirements. The marketed surplus is that quantity of the produce which is actually sold by the farmer in the market irrespective of his requirements. Thus, marketed surplus includes 'distress sale' by farmers (majority

small and marginal) owing to cash needs for discharging their immediate liabilities and for purchasing of all necessities for the family. Marketable surplus can be less, equal or even more than the marketable surplus.

In this study the amount of paddy sold to the market by the farmer irrespective of his other considerations is termed as marketable surplus and analyzed accordingly.

1.2 Objectives

The objectives of the study are to:

Estimate the marketable surplus and analyze marketing channels

Analyze the relative income loss in various channels by estimating PS and ME

Assess the factors affecting Marketable Surplus of paddy

1.3 Methodology

The primary data collected 474 farm households across various farm sizes of three villages with varied irrigation status drawn from three different blocks of Subarnapur district of Odisha during the year 2023-24. The farm sizes are classified as Small (upto 5.00 acres), Medium (5.01 acres to 10 acres) and Large (10.01 acres and above) based on operational land holdings. The marketable surplus is viewed as the quantity of output sold in the market by the farmers. The Prevailing system of market and marketing channels (both formal and informal) for paddy has been considered such as Channel-I, II and III. The Cost of Marketing includes cost of transportation, loading and unloading, cost for storage, and cost for packaging etc.. The cost of inputs used includes the cost of fertilizer, pesticide, human labour, bullock and machine labour etc. The Minimum Support Price {MSP} has been considered to estimate the PS. The actual price prevailing in Channel-I and II during year or seasons in the area under study has been considered for estimating the money value of marketable surplus under these channels. Similarly, the actual price received from Channel-III has been considered even though Channel-III is supposed to offer MSP (due to the deduction of certain amount of paddy per bag on the ground of grading, standardization and quality of paddy etc.). The factors affecting the marketable surplus of paddy across farm sizes

and villages has been analyzed by Linear Regression (OLS) Model along with Chow-test to test the significant difference between/among the regression lines.

1. 4 Paddy Procurement System in the study area

The market was earlier deregulated and mostly handled by private traders and rice millers which resulted in distress sale of paddy. Thus subsequently, reforms in agricultural marketing took place and the market was open to both the private and government agencies for paddy procurement directly from the farmers. But after the amendment of the APMC Act in 2007 the private agencies were not allowed for paddy procurement in the state of Odisha. As a result of which the market for paddy procurement became completely regulated and government/ government supported (such as cooperatives and others) agencies have been procuring the paddy since then. The Primary Agricultural Cooperative Societies (PACs) have been engaged as commission agent of Odisha State Civil Supply Corporation (OSCSC) in the state of Odisha since the year 2009 for paddy procurement.

1.5 Marketable Surplus of Paddy and Marketing Channels

The Marketable Surplus of paddy (i.e. quantity of output sold) across the villages and farm sizes has been shown in Table-1.5.1. The number of Marketing Channels of Paddy and percentage of output sold through various channels by different farm sizes in various villages has been depicted in table-1.5.2.

1.5.1 Marketable Surplus

The table 1.5.1 shows that the marketable surplus as a percentage of output per acre/ farm varies directly with the farm sizes irrespective of the irrigation status of the villages. Further, the share of marketable surplus in output is relatively found much lower for small farms in V-II and V-III which may be due to the effect of inadequate irrigation, higher proportion of retention for consumption and the farm size. However, the degree of variation in the share of marketable surplus to output is found more for all farm sizes in V-I compared to that of V-II and V-III.

The cost of production (input cost) as a percentage of marketable surpluses is found directly related to the farm size irrespective of the villages. This may be due to the

size effect and affordability of input use by higher farm sizes than that of small. It indicates technical efficiency (cost effectiveness) and hence relatively higher net marketable surplus of small farms.

The marketing cost is also found increases with the increase in farm sizes as majority of large and medium farms sold relatively higher proportion of their marketable surplus in order to dispose of their product soon after harvesting due to lack of proper market infrastructure and cost involved toward the safety of their products till its auction. Thus the marketing cost due to transportation and temporary safe storage of their bulk products is comparatively higher for large and medium farms.

1.5.2 Channels of Paddy Marketing

The existing paddy marketing channels (informal and formal) in the area under study are categorized into three such as:

Channel-I:Farmersto traders / commission agents /brokers of village market. It is easily accessible but more prone to distress sale due to linkage of informal credit (cash/kind) to output sale.

Channel-II: Farmers to agents/brokers of rice millers in village market.It is as good as open market for farmers, easily accessible and offerslightly higher price than Channel-I but less than MSP.

Channel-III: Farmers to Cooperatives / regulated markets. The operational modalities are guided by government norms. The accessibility is relatively difficult mainly for small farmsdue to official formalities and delay in receiving payments even though MSP is ensured subject to thefulfillment of required standard of their produces.

The table-1.5.2 reveals that the percentage of households and proportion output sold in Channel-I and Channel-II is inversely related to farm sizes. It means the higher percentage of Small farms selling higher proportion of their marketable surplus of paddy in Channel-I and Channel-II. But the percentage of households and proportion output sold in Channel-III is found directly related to Farm sizes as relatively higher percentage of large and medium farms are found selling higher proportion of their

marketable surplus of paddy through this channel. This indicates that the advantage of regulated market is accrued to higher farm sizes.

1.6 Producers' Share in consumers' rupees (PS) and Marketing Efficiency (ME)

The PS and ME have been estimated to assess the remunerative behaviour and efficiency of each of the channels across various farm sizes and villages under study. The PS is the ratio of the price received by the farmer to the price paid by the customer (here MSP is considered as consumer price) expressed as the percentage.

$$P_s = (P_{rf}/P_{pc}) \times 100$$

Where,

P_s = Producers' share

P_{rf} = Price received by farmers

P_{pc} = Price paid by consumers

The ME is measured as the ratio of total value of goods marketed to the marketing cost. This ratio is directly related to the efficiency.

Index of Marketing Efficiency (ME) =

$$[\{\text{Value of goods sold (at consumers' price)}\} / \{\text{Total marketing cost}\} - 1]$$

The table-1.6 reveals that the PS and ME in Channel-I and II is found relatively higher for small farms than that of medium and large farm sizes.. This can be attributed to higher dependency of small farms on the interlocked market i.e. mainly channel-I. The rate paddy is much below the MSP in this channel but whatever rate this channel offers it is relatively higher for small farms as because the buyers (traders/commission agents) were most concern about recovering their debt with exorbitant rate of interest amicably which will enhance their gain if recovered fully so they would not hesitate to offer some higher price to them which will conversely encourage the small farms to maintain the same type of credit-output linkage with them. After fulfilling their commitment through Channel-I certain proportion their residual surplus mainly sold to Channel-II where the rate of paddy offered is comparatively higher than that of Channel-I and also unlike Channel-I, there is no pre-requisite commitment while trading with Channel-II. Further both of these channels are easily accessible to small farms and available at their door steps with least marketing cost. So the marketing

efficiency of small farms under these two channels is found relatively higher as marketing cost is least.

Further, the PS is found inversely and marketing efficiency is directly related to farm sizes in Channel-III. It means the PS is found relatively higher for small farms which may be due to the quality aspects of their products better taken care as the volume sold by them through Channel-III is very less and hence more remunerative. But the marketing efficiency of small farms is found less than that of large and medium farm sizes in Channel-III as because the small farms are less accessible to this Channel may be due to less quantity of residual surplus, higher transaction cost or marketing cost, more formalities and delay in receiving payments against their products etc. Thus in Channel-III the marketing efficiency lies with large and medium farms.

1.7 Proportion of income loss and Distress Sale

The proportion of income loss estimated from the price difference between the various channels and the proportion of distress sale of paddy are represented by Table-1.7. The proportion of income loss due to difference in the prices of the products sold in various channels is found less for small farms compared to other farm sizes as per the advantages of each of the channels availed by the small farms as mentioned in the preceding discussion. However, the magnitude of income loss due to the price difference between Channel-I & III is found higher in all the villages and for all farm sizes. This indicates that even though the loss proportion is relatively less for small farms, it is not an indication that the small farms are gainer rather they are looser as only a small quantity of well graded and standardized surplus of paddy is sold in Channel-III but higher proportion of its products sold in Channel-I. Thus, the amount of income loss of small farmers in the entire area under study matter much keeping in view their less quantity of marketable surplus of which higher proportion is sold to Channel-I (Interlocked market). Thus, the percentage of distress sale of paddy by small farms is found higher compared to other farm sizes in all the villages under study. The approximate loss of income per bag of paddy due to distress sale is same for all farm sizes of a village. However, the loss is found higher in V-III (rain fed village) compared to that of V-I (irrigated village) and V-II (semi-irrigated village) as shown in the table. On an average, for the entire sample case the loss is found around

Rs. 93/- per bag of paddy which possess challenges against the existing regulated market mechanism of the state to overcome the problems of distress sale in which all farm sizes in general and small farm size in particular are suffering adversely.

1.8 Factors Affecting Marketable Surplus

There are various factors affecting marketable surplus of paddy across the villages such as V-I, V-II and V-III and Farm sizes such as Small, Medium and Large. In order to assess this linear (OLS) regression analysis has been used and to test the significance difference between the regression lines estimated for various villages and farm sizes Chow-Test (F value) has been conducted and the results are depicted in Table-1.8. The regression equation is follows.

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \dots + \beta_{12} X_{12} + u_i$$

Where α is the intercept and $\beta_1 \dots \beta_{12}$ are the partial regression coefficients

u_i is the stochastic disturbance terms

Y = Marketable Surplus of Rice (paddy) per acre of GCA (in Rupees)

X_1 = production of rice (paddy) per acre of GCA (in Rupees)

X_2 = Household size (Nos.),

X_3 = Credit (credit from all sources) per acre (in Rupees)

X_4 = Area leased in to Net area operated (in Percentage)

X_5 = Area under HYV to GCA (in Percentage)

X_6 = Quality of land (Dummy if Low land=1, otherwise= 0),

X_7 = Use of Bullock & Machine labour per acre (in Rupees)

X_8 = Use of Fertilizer per acre (in Rupees)

X_9 = Use of Pesticide per acre (in Rupees)

X_{10} = Use of Human labour per acre (in Rupees)

X_{11} = Education (No. of years of Schooling)

X_{12} = Proportion of Marketable Surplus sold to Regulated Market (in Percentage)

The regression results for the above stated function were worked out for various farm sizes and villages and to test the significant difference between/ among the regression lines "Chow test" was undertaken and 'F' value computed if the 'F' exceeds the

critical F value at the chosen level of α , reject the hypotheses that the regressions estimated for various fam sizes or villages (whichever the case is) are the same.

Given the assumptions of the Chow test procedure, it can be shown as follows:

$$F = \frac{S_6/K}{S_5/(N_1 + N_2 + N_3 - 3K)}$$

Follows the 'F' distribution with $df = (K, N_1+N_2+N_3-3K)$.

For instance, where, K = number of parameter estimated (i.e. 13) and N_1, N_2 & N_3 are no. of observations of the various groups (small, medium and large farms respectively).

$S_6 = S_1 - S_5$, where S_1 = Residual sum of square (RSS) for pooled data, S_2, S_3 and S_4 are the RSS for small, medium and large groups respectively. df is degree of freedom

In this study there exist significant difference between/ among the regression lines estimated for the villages and farm sizes as revealed by Chow-test (F value) shown in the table. Thus factors affecting the marketable surplus of paddy may be analyzed across the villages and farm sizes.

The regression results reveal that X_1 and X_2 have significantly positive and negative relationship with Y respectively across the villages and farm sizes, It means irrespective of the villages and farm sizes the marketable surplus increases with the increase in paddy productivity and decreases with the increase in Household size. Bigger the size of family, higher will be the quantity of paddy retention for household consumption and hence lower will be the marketable surplus. Further, X_3 is found negative and significantly related to Y in V-II, Small farms, Large farms and All-V (entire sample). This may be attributed to the diversion of farm credit from the purpose of production to other purposes (may be for consumption and others). It is found that X_4 is positive and significantly related to Y across the villages and farm sizes (it is positive but not significant for medium farms). It indicates that tenancy has a positive impact on marketable surplus. It is observed that X_5 is negative and significantly related to Y for V-II, Large farms and All-V but significantly positive relationship with Y for V-III and Medium farms. It is negatively related (not significant) for V-I and Small farms. The negative relationship may be attributed to lack of irrigation facility, inadequate use of technology, excess use of HYV seed or

excess use of fertilizers/ pesticide. The factor like X_6 is found positive and significantly related to Y in V-II and All-V. In other cases it is found positive but not significant. So except certain few and specific cases the quality of land has less impact on the marketable surplus. It is found that X_7 has positive and significant relationship with Y for V-III, Small farms and All-V but it is negative and significant for medium farms. The negative and positive relationship may be due to the excess and judicious use of it respectively. The X_8 is positively related to Y across the villages and farm sizes but found positive and significant for V-II, V-III, All-V and Large farms. However, higher the use of fertilizers can lead to higher productivity and hence higher marketable surplus. Similarly, the X_9 is found positive and significantly related to Y in V-I, V-II and All-V but found significantly negative for Small farms which may be due the injudicious use of pesticide attributed to the lack of affordability of small farms to use it on time. The X_{10} is negative and significantly related to Y for V-II, All-V, Small farms, Medium Farms and Large Farms. This may be attributed to higher retention of paddy for payment of wages to human labour for various farming operations which causes less marketable surplus. The X_{11} has positive and significant relationship with Y in V-II and All-V. It indicates that except some specific cases education has no impact on marketable surplus irrespective of the villages and farm sizes rather in certain cases it is negative even though not significant. The X_{12} is positive and significantly related to Y across the villages ((it is only positive for V-III) and Farmsizes. It indicates that expectation to sell the paddy in regulate market with remunerative price (i.e. MSP) as observed from the their past behavior i.e. the Proportion of paddy sold to Regulated Market encourages them to have more marketable surplus either by increasing paddy productivity or decreasing retention of paddy for consumption and other purposes.

1.9 Conclusion

The marketable surplus varies directly with the farm sizes irrespective of the irrigation status of the villages under study. However, the degree of variation in the share of marketable surplus to output is found relatively higher for irrigated village. The proportion of input cost of production to marketable surpluses is found directly related to farm sizes. The marketing cost is also found directly related to the farm size.

The percentage of Small farms and the marketable surplus of paddy sold in Channel-I and Channel-II are found higher than that of large and medium farms who sold higher proportion of their marketable surplus of paddy in Channel-III. This indicates higher farm sizes are drawing more advantages from the regulated market system. The PS and ME in Channel-I and Channel-II are found relatively higher for small farms. The PS is found inversely related to farm sizes and ME is directly related to farm sizes in Channel-III

The proportion of income loss due to difference in the prices of the products sold in various channels is found less for small farms compared to other farm sizes. However, the magnitude of income loss due to the price difference between Channel-I & III is found higher. The percentage of distress sale of paddy by small farms is found higher compared to higher farmsizes. The loss of income per bag of paddy due to distress sale is found higher in V-III (rain fed village) compared to that of other villages. On an average, for the entire sample case the loss is found around Rs. 93/- per bag of paddy which possess challenges against the existing market mechanism to overcome the problems of distress sale.

The factors most commonly and significantly affecting Marketable surplus of paddy per acre are X_1 , X_2 , X_{12} where X_1 and X_{12} are positively but X_2 is negatively related to Marketable surplus of paddy irrespective of the villages and farm sizes.

The existing regulated or government driven market for paddy procurement may be revamped and made more competitive to provide price assurance and protection towards the empowerment of farmers in general and small farmers in particular so as to ensure higher productivity, marketable surplus and income.

Table-1.5.1: Marketable Surplus of paddy across farm sizes and villages

Village / farm Size	Marketable surplus to output per acre/farm (in%)	No. of households	% of households	Input Cost of production to Marketing surplus per acre (in %)	Marketing cost per bag
Village (V) -I					
Small	72.09	84.00	43.75	65.84	4.71
Medium	85.17	52.00	27.08	68.34	5.99
Large	92.61	56.00	29.17	66.10	7.16
ALL	87.37	192.00	100.00	66.55	6.55
V-II					

Small	34.80	86.00	61.87	69.81	4.96
Medium	79.40	24.00	17.27	72.70	5.94
Large	85.77	29.00	20.86	75.56	6.71
ALL	73.11	139.00	100.00	73.00	6.32
V-III					
Small	32.72	82.00	57.34	89.00	3.34
Medium	64.03	53.00	37.06	92.00	4.64
Large	72.88	8.00	5.59	94.82	7.47
ALL	53.80	143.00	100.00	92.00	4.86
All-V					
Small	57.58	252.00	53.16	74.88	4.59
Medium	79.80	129.00	27.22	77.68	5.75
Large	90.93	93.00	19.62	78.83	7.09
ALL	81.32	474.00	100.00	77.18	6.39

Note: One Bag of Paddy= 75 kg

Table-1.5.2: Proportion of output sold through various Marketing Channels across farm sizes and villages

Villages /Farm sizes	Channel-I		Channel-II		Channel-III	
	No. of households Sold their product	Proportion of output sold (in %)	No. of households Sold their product	Proportion of output sold (in %)	No. of households Sold their product	Proportion of output sold (in %)
V-I						
Small	70.00	48.22	44.00	21.00	28.00	30.61
Medium	44.00	25.69	28.00	24.55	32.00	49.76
Large	47.00	19.65	26.00	11.08	50.00	69.27
ALL	161.00	25.08	98.00	15.43	110.00	59.47
V-II						
Small	28.00	51.47	3.00	15.82	16.00	32.71
Medium	16.00	37.05	7.00	13.97	13.00	48.98
Large	22.00	26.59	7.00	11.59	21.00	61.82
ALL	66.00	32.05	17.00	12.69	50.00	55.26
V-III						
Small	56.00	79.39	7.00	14.94	2.00	5.67
Medium	50.00	54.52	18.00	18.08	20.00	27.40
Large	5.00	20.77	1.00	4.72	7.00	74.50
ALL	111.00	53.96	26.00	14.98	29.00	31.06
All-V						
Small	154.00	55.14	54.00	19.66	46.00	25.07
Medium	110.00	35.47	53.00	22.36	65.00	42.17
Large	74.00	19.70	34.00	10.76	78.00	69.53
ALL	338.00	29.60	141.00	15.36	189.00	55.02

Table-1.6: PS and ME across various Channels, farm sizes and villages

Villages /Farm sizes	Channel-I		Channel-II		channel-III	
	PS	ME	PS	ME	PS	ME
V-I						
Small	83.60	89.73	90.71	41.89	94.19	67.91
Medium	82.74	36.29	86.64	36.32	93.33	86.29
Large	80.69	22.06	87.90	13.17	92.53	99.77
ALL	82.29	31.89	88.34	20.72	92.80	93.80
V-II						
Small	82.44	89.55	90.82	29.67	94.13	68.80
Medium	80.88	51.96	90.04	21.23	93.30	85.56
Large	80.46	32.29	89.08	15.06	92.80	95.20
ALL	81.08	42.05	89.71	17.85	93.00	90.55
V-III						
Small	82.86	205.77	91.43	41.95	93.33	16.83
Medium	81.34	99.26	91.43	36.38	93.33	60.95
Large	81.43	22.78	91.43	5.07	93.33	103.72
ALL	81.84	94.34	91.43	28.57	93.33	66.05
All-V						
Small	83.16	99.07	90.73	40.38	94.15	63.91
Medium	82.01	47.69	87.95	33.62	93.33	82.70
Large	80.73	23.65	87.95	13.28	92.58	99.15
ALL	82.25	36.88	88.84	20.70	92.85	91.78

Table-1.7: Proportion of income loss between channels and Distress Sale across farm sizes and villages

	proportion of income loss per bag between channels-I &II	proportion of income loss per bag between channels-I &III	proportion of income loss per bag between channels-II &III	Percentage of Distress Sale (in bags)	Average amount of income loss (approx.) due to distress sale per bag (in Rs.)
V-I					
Small	8.51	19.62	10.24	69.22	87.00
Medium	4.71	20.86	15.42	50.24	87.00
Large	8.93	23.93	13.77	30.73	87.00
ALL	7.35	21.52	13.20	40.50	87.00
V-II					
Small	10.17	21.30	10.11	67.29	96.00
Medium	11.32	23.63	11.07	51.02	96.00
Large	10.71	24.29	12.26	38.18	96.00
ALL	10.65	23.33	11.46	44.74	96.00
V-III					

Small	10.34	20.69	9.38	94.33	111.00
Medium	12.41	22.95	9.38	72.60	111.00
Large	12.28	22.81	9.38	25.50	111.00
ALL	11.72	22.19	9.38	68.94	111.00
All-V					
Small	9.11	20.26	10.22	74.80	93.00
Medium	7.25	21.94	13.70	57.83	93.00
Large	8.94	23.87	13.70	30.47	93.00
ALL	8.01	21.58	12.56	44.96	93.00

Table-1.8: Factors Affecting the Marketable Surplus across villages and Farm Sizes (Regression Results)

Dependent Variable: Marketable Surplus of paddy per acre of GCA (in Rs.)							
	Village - I	Village - II	Village - III	Small	Medium	Large	All Village
	Coefficient	Coefficient	Coefficient	Coefficient	Coefficient	Coefficient	Coefficient
(Constant)	-6689.3* (-9.53)	-1828.4 (-1.24)	-5651.8 * (-12.66)	-6048.5 * (-15.31)	-3195.5* (-5.97)	-1988.21 * (-8.97)	-5471.2 * (-16.82)
X ₁	1.50* (16.32)	0.64 *** (1.81)	1.13 * (14.76)	1.46 * (18.73)	1.12 * (16.16)	1.30 * (30.50)	1.14 * (17.88)
X ₂	-54.14* (-4.18)	-91.90 *** (-1.93)	-66.20 * (-3.17)	-83.77 ** (-2.44)	-86.97 * (-6.20)	-47.61 * (-6.39)	-35.55 ** (-2.25)
X ₃	-0.36 (-0.34)	-0.08 ** (-2.11)	0.06 (0.59)	-0.06 ** (-2.47)	-0.03 (-0.56)	-0.15 ** (-2.79)	-0.09 * (-4.60)
X ₄	365.16* (2.85)	2118.41 * (5.52)	210.04 *** (1.86)	1216.9 * (5.33)	41.69 (0.42)	327.17 * (3.16)	1224.6 * (7.93)
X ₅	-3.37 (-0.30)	-19.14 * (-3.33)	7.18 ** (2.26)	-2.81 (-0.85)	9.65 ** (2.28)	-11.44 ** (-2.29)	-12.71 ** (-2.84)
X ₆	75.36 (0.92)	698.44 * (3.42)	78.57 (1.32)	178.24 (1.38)	54.71 (1.25)	-48.11 (-0.97)	345.27 * (3.63)
X ₇	0.25 (0.33)	-2.13 (-1.46)	2.09 ** (2.48)	4.77 * (7.38)	-0.10 * (-0.12)	-0.63 (-1.95)	3.51 * (6.08)
X ₈	0.26 (0.28)	3.26 ** (2.86)	2.60 * (8.37)	0.32 (0.37)	0.59 (0.93)	1.47 * (4.04)	3.02 * (11.19)
X ₉	5.61* (4.47)	7.30 * (4.43)	2.29 (1.09)	-3.40 * (-3.75)	-0.40 (-0.72)	0.90 (1.48)	1.56 ** (2.28)
X ₁₀	-0.12 (-0.89)	-0.86 * (-3.04)	0.004 (0.01)	-0.77 * (-4.45)	-0.26 ** (-2.04)	-0.25 ** (-2.42)	-0.54 * (-3.21)
X ₁₁	-5.01 (-0.44)	54.20 *** (1.83)	-8.56 (-0.93)	7.81 (0.50)	2.96 (0.49)	-0.28 (-0.06)	23.56 *** (1.92)
X ₁₂	5.25* (5.02)	9.16 * (3.38)	0.58 (0.57)	8.26 * (4.29)	1.98 ** (2.89)	1.97 ** (2.39)	7.67 * (4.91)
F	120.06*	62.74 *	155.24 *	180.61 *	584.15*	761.08 *	195.13 *
R ²	0.83	0.74	0.92	0.84	0.91	0.92	0.83
N	192	139	143	252	129	93	474
Chow Test F _{13, 453}	31.7 *			21.1 *			

NB. Robust standard Error is estimated for this regression model.

Figures in the parenthesis indicate 't' statistics

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